

Reproducibility Report for the Paper: CosRec: 2D Convolutional Neural Networks for Sequential Recommendation

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Nowadays, reproducibility has become the main core of the scientific method. Standardization and documentation of the workflow is important to show that the paper outcomes and the related studies are likely reproducible. In this report we go through the reproducibility analysis for the paper *CosRec: 2D Convolutional Neural Networks for Sequential Recommendation*. In particular, a detailed analysis of the settings and the statistical significance of the results is presented.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: reproducibility, CosRec, neural networks

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1 INTRODUCTION

The paper *CosRec: 2D Convolutional Neural Networks for Sequential Recommendation* by An Yan, Shuo Cheng, Wang-Cheng Kang, Mengting Wan, Julian McAuley [Yan et al. 2019] presents experimental results related to the performance of a 2D convolutional network for sequential recommendation (CosRec). The authors demonstrate that modeling pairwise relationships directly leads to an efficient representation of sequential features and captures complex item correlations. Moreover, they demonstrate that such a model can cover complex relationship in user purchase histories. The authors validate their theoretical results by means of a network architecture made up by three different layers, written in Python. The authors have also compared the quantitative results on two public datasets (Movielens and Gowalla) with the conventional existing methods that either use or not the sequential features, achieving state-of-the-art performance on various evaluation metrics.

In first we analyzed the paper to understand the state of the art and what the authors want to demonstrate, then we tried to replicate the results and to do a detailed analysis of the potential reproducibility drawbacks.

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2 SOFTWARE DOWNLOAD AND INSTALLATION

The authors have provided a link to a public repository on GitHub (<https://github.com/zzxslp/CosRec>), making the code and the processed datasets available. To simplify the implementation process they provided the instructions to run the code with the two different datasets.

The software requirements of the project are:

- Python 3
- PyTorch v1.0+

The authors specified that the presented results are obtained on a Linux server (w/ NVIDIA GeForce Titan X Pascal) with PyTorch 1.1.0 and Python 3.7.

The authors have not provided a docker environment to run the simulations hence we created a local virtual environment with the specified requirements to perform the tests.

2.1 Dataset Preprocessing Steps

The provided datasets are:

- MovieLens [Harper and Konstan 2015]: A widely used benchmark dataset for evaluating collaborative filtering algorithms. We use the MovieLens-1M (ML-1M) version in our experiments.
- Gowalla [Cho et al. 2011]: A location-based social networking website where users share their locations by checking-in, labeled with time stamps.

These two datasets are preprocessed by following a procedure presented by Caser [Tang and Wang 2018], in order to compare the results among different methods (state of the art), and divided with the holdout method in training, validation and test set (70/10/20) by following a time based splitting. Moreover, they converted all numeric ratings to implicit feedback (0/1) that indicates if an item is rated or not. Thus, for each dataset we have the user id, the item id and the implicit feedback columns.

Since the datasets are already provided, we tried to replicate preprocessing steps for the Movielens ML-1M dataset by following the same procedure stated in the paper and in the related works [Tang and Wang 2018]. This because we want to get the results from different data splitting (also with cross validation) and to understand how it was done. We found that the preprocessing steps are clear and that there

Dataset	Metric	Cos-Rec Base	Cos-Rec	Test 1	Test 2
ML - 1M	MAP	0.1743	0.1883	0.1886	0.1885
	Prec@1	0.2892	0.3308	0.3296	0.3313
	Prec@5	0.2521	0.2831	0.2789	0.2805
	Prec@10	0.2256	0.2493	0.2480	0.2476
	Recall@1	0.0186	0.0202	0.0203	0.0205
	Recall@5	0.0771	0.0843	0.0818	0.0838
	Recall@10	0.1331	0.1438	0.1415	0.1431
Gowalla	MAP	0.0821	0.0980	0.0844	.
	Prec@1	0.1712	0.2135	0.2109	.
	Prec@5	0.1012	0.1190	0.1131	.
	Prec@10	0.0884	0.993	0.928	NA
	Recall@1	0.0265	0.0337	0.0306	.
	Recall@5	0.0752	0.0890	0.0892	.
	Recall@10	0.1107	0.1305	0.1294	.

Table 1. Results obtained over different machines

are several references to different works that we analyzed in order to achieve the same results. However, there found some drawbacks.

The problems that we encountered for the Movielens Dataset are:

- We can not apply cross validation because the dataset is time-based splitted
- The dataset that we obtain from the preprocessing are not the same as the train , validation and test sets provided.

3 COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS

The replication of the experiments has been carried out on multiple machines running different operative systems to provide determinism and portability of the results. The utilized machines are:

- AMD A10-9600 CPU clocked at 2.4GHz, running Windows 10 OS
- Intel CoreTM i7-500U 2.4GHz with Turbo Boost up to 3.0GHz, running Ubuntu 18.04

The code is easy to run, but it takes different running times depending on the utilized machine and the use or not of CUDA (*Compute Unified Device Architecture*). In particular it took more than 1 day to run over the 40 epochs with the CPU only machine and about 3 hours to run over the same epochs with the CUDA flag.

The results that we obtained from the Github code are presented in the Table 1. In the columns *Test 1, 2* the results for the first and the second machine are presented. It was not possible to run the code with the Gowalla dataset on the second machine due to the hardware limitation (in particular

the RAM was too low). We can easily see and ascertain that the results are similar to the results presented in the paper with a very slight difference. Thus, we can confirm the overall results.

4 CUSTOM PREPROCESSING

Fig. 1. Cross Validation Method for Time base splitting

Additionally to the already provided processed data we decided to apply and propose another preprocessing strategy to be able to perform some statistical testing. In fact, the original strategy was to apply a time-splitting based method. The idea is to apply a timestamp-based cross-validation with $k = 10$ since it is a method that allows us to apply some statistical testing (e.g. paired t-test).

To split the data in a proper way let U be the User-ID and U_{max} the maximum number of different users (e.g. for the ML-1M is 6040). For each k -cross validation split the algorithm takes the i -th User-ID and do a reordering (increasing) of the time-stamps. Then it apply a cross validation only on the i -th User-ID and store it into a separated data-frame in a test and

train part (80% train 20% test). This procedure was done for each users. (see fig.1) The original preprocessing algorithm presents only an holdout method (70/10/20) with the same time-stamp strategy.

5 ADDITIONAL PERFORMANCE TESTING

We also provided additional performance results for the two different neural networks (CosRec-Base with MLP and the proposed Cos-Rec). We defined a computational efficiency factor $\eta = \frac{MAP}{t_R}$, where MAP is the Mean Average Precision and t_R is the measured inference-time + train-time. Another performance metric that we provided is the F1-score that allow us to understand which classifier is better and gives us additional information over the original performance metrics. The F1-score for the 10-timestamp cross-validation (see the result table 2) is calculated by the mean value over the 10 folds. When we compared the results to the test set we could see that the computational efficiency is larger for the proposed CosRec-Base against the the CosRec with CNN classifier. Overall the MAP score behaviors almost in the same way in respect to the method without cross validation. The F1-score is higher for the CosRec classifiers and also for the CV data-set.

6 STATISTICAL SETTINGS

In this paper the authors only compared the results in terms of best MAP and they conclude their hypothesis by analyzing the gain between the proposed CosRec Neural Network and the results from the state of the art (e.g. Markov Chain, Recurrent Neural Network). Therefore, no statistical testing was provided. It was also difficult to set up a statistical testing on this data since we also tried the time-based cross validation to understand all the possible drawbacks. Thus, we can not apply any statistical test (paired or unpaired).

We identified the possible cause of this problem in the state of the art studies since they didn't provide any further information about the statistical property of the tests and it seems that they did not give much importance on that.

With the proposed preprocessing step (time based cross validation) we could apply a paired t-test to see if the two models, the MLP based and the proposed CosRec Neural Network, have a significant difference in statistical terms.

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{s_{\bar{d}}}$$

$$\bar{d} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N d_i$$

$$s_{\bar{d}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^N d_i)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$d_i = x_{A,i} - x_{B,i}$$

where $x_{A,i}$ is the i th element from the first network, $A = \text{Cos-Rec}$, $B = \text{Cos-Rec-Base}$ and x is the corresponding score (the MAP in our case).

We performed the test with *GraphPad PRISM 8* software by fixing the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Finally we get a two-tailed P value less than 0.0001 and we could conclude, by conventional criteria, that this difference is extremely significant. Thus we can reject the null hypothesis and state that the CosRec outperform the basis with the MLP implementation.

About the confidence interval, the difference in case of the mean values of the two groups are -0.00945 with a 95% of confidence.

Fig. 2. Computational result for the proposed Cos-Rec and the MLP based Cos-Rec_base

7 FLAWS

By comparing our values with the results stated in the paper we can see that we get very similar results in terms of the considered performance metrics (Precision, Recall, MAP). However, one of the major flaw that we found is that the preprocessing steps of the MovieLens dataset, that we tried to reproduce on the raw version downloaded by the indicated source link, lead to a different training and test set. Moreover, we noticed some inconsistency in the provided data since some user is linked to items that are not considered in the original one. Furthermore, statistical testing is missing and it was not possible to perform that on the provided output and results for the causes mentioned before, hence we tried to propose a possible solution for that that was not too simple to implement since the data preparation does not follow a standard holdout method.

Dataset	Metric	Cos-Rec Base	Cos-Rec	Cos-Rec Base CV 10	Cos-Rec CV 10
ML - 1M	η	0.001134	0.000737	0.001285	0.000812
	F1@1	0.033887	0.034986	0.036252	0.180173
	F1@5	0.115383	0.119868	0.120850	0.124633
	F1@10	0.165008	0.171921	0.175275	0.180173

Table 2. F1 score and computational results for the time-based cross validation

8 CONCLUSION

In general we can state that the paper and the workflow is well documented and that it was good to try to get some different settings from the data and to perform some analysis on them. The more challenging part is to re-process the provided train and test data. The strategy was given by the related papers and we followed the same steps but we figured out that we could not reprocess it properly; moreover, further research on that flaw did not bring us to a solution on that problem. A possible solution could be to contact the authors and have a thorough explanation.

We also understood how difficult is to have a setting that facilitates the statistical testing in a time based splitting approach and sequential systems and how is difficult to apply the cross validation on that setting. We also touched by hand our hardware drawbacks and understood how it is difficult

to reproduce some scientific results in a reasonable amount of time without scientific facilities (e.g. GPUs, TPUs).

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